

Effect of Dilution, Dialysis and Non-Electrolytes on the Stability of Ferric Tellurate Sol

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Coagulation constants, 'a', 'm' and 'n' of Bhattacharya's equation⁴ $C = a + \left(\frac{m \cdot 1/t}{n + 1/t} \right)$ for ferric tellurate sol, at various stages of dilution and dialysis and as well as in the presence of non-electrolytes, have been studied during its slow coagulation using KCl, K₂SO₄ and K₃Fe(CN)₆ as coagulants. The progressive dialysis has been found to cause a marked decrease in the value of each constant. Addition of increasing volume of sensitising non-electrolytes (methanol, ethanol, isopropanol, acetone, formamide and dioxane) causes a decrease in the values of a, (a+m) and n and the reverse effect is obtained with stabilising non-electrolytes (glycerol and urea).

In continuation to our previous publications¹⁻³ on the effect of dilution, dialysis and non-electrolytes on the coagulation constants of ferric hydroxide, stannic hydroxide and silver sols, we have extended our studies on the coagulation of ferric tellurate sol. The present communication deals with an attempt to study the variation of 'a', 'm' and 'n' constants of Bhattacharya's equation⁴, at different dilutions of the sol, and also at different periods of dialysis. The values of these constants have also been evaluated in the presence of different non-electrolytes to throw light on the stabilising or sensitising power of the non-electrolytes used.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ferric tellurate sol was prepared by adding a 6% solution of potassium tellurate to a 4% solution of FeCl₃ with constant stirring until the precipitate just ceased to dissolve. The precipitate so formed was peptised by adding FeCl₃ solution in excess. A reddish brown sol was obtained which was dialysed in a parchment paper bag. Three different samples of the sol were prepared. One sample was used for the study of the effect of dilution, the second for the effect of dialysis and the third for the study of non-electrolyte effect

Time of coagulation of the sol, using KCl, K₂SO₄ and K₃Fe(CN)₆ as coagulating electrolytes, was determined by Light Extinction Method, using a "Gallenkamp" Photoelectric

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3. M. Singh and O. P. Bansal, *Bull. Chem. Soc.*, Japan (in press).
4. A. K. Bhattacharya and R. Kumar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **28**, 179, 638; 1952, **29**, 687, 759; *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1955, **10**, 551.

Colorimeter and the constants (a , m and n) were found graphically^{5,6}. The values of the constants obtained for the same stage of coagulation given by the same extinction value for the sol at different stages of dilution and dialysis, and also in the presence of different amounts of various non-electrolytes have been recorded in Tables I, II and III.

DISCUSSION

Bhattacharya's equation, $C = a + \frac{m \cdot 1/t}{n+1/t}$ may be put in the form $1/(C-a) = (n/m)t + 1/m$ which shows that the plot $1/(C-a)$ against t should be a straight line and this has actually been observed in all cases of the present studies (Figs. not given for the economy of the space) confirming the applicability of the equation for the coagulation of the sol by electrolytes, in the partially dialysed state and also in the presence of non-electrolytes.

If $1/t$ is made large as compared to ' n ' the equation $C = a + \frac{m \cdot 1/t}{n+1/t}$ takes up the form $C = a + m$. This means that ' m ' is the excess of the electrolyte that should be added above the critical stability concentration ' a ' in order to cause the immediate coagulation of the sol. It may be said that at $C = a + m$, the region of slow coagulation merges into that of rapid coagulation. From Table I it is evident that the value of $(a+m)$ of the univalent precipitating ion (Cl^-) increases with the dilution that of bivalent (SO_4^{--}) and trivalent [$\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{--}$] decreases. From this it may be concluded that ferric tellurate sol upon dilution becomes more stable towards univalent precipitating ion but less stable towards bi- and tri-valent ions.

Three factors appear to determine the effect of dilution of sol on the stability : (i) the smaller number of particles in the weaker sol requires less electrolyte to lower the zeta potential to the coagulation point; (ii) the decreased chance of collision requires a lower potential, and hence more electrolyte, to effect coagulation; and (iii) the ion having the same sign of charge as the sol has a stabilising effect. Consequently the normality or abnormality of the dilution effect depends upon the combined influence of these factors. The influence of the dilution of sol is also contaminated by other effects. Hence dilution of a hydrophobic colloid is not at all an innocent process. With dilution peptising and contaminating electrolytes are also diluted and this may give rise either to a decrease or an increase of stability.

The values of the constants a , m and n decrease with the progressive dialysis of the sol (Table II). As the dialysis of the sol continues, its stabilising electrolyte is removed and so it becomes increasingly sensitive and hence its region of slow coagulation merges into that of rapid coagulation at lower concentration of the coagulating electrolyte, as evidenced by the decrease in the value of $(a+m)$, with the period of dialysis.

The non-electrolytes which sensitise the coagulation process of ferric tellurate sol towards KCl , K_2SO_4 and $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ electrolytes are found to decrease the values of a ,

5. A. K. Bhattacharya and A. Kumar, *Agra. Univ. J. Res. Sci.*, 1963, **12**, 101; *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1956, **11**, 124.

6. M. Singh, *J. Pract. Chem.*, 1968, **38**, 276.

TABLE I

Effect of dilution
Concentration of the sol (A) = 12.25 g./litre

Electrolyte	<i>a</i> (mM/l)			<i>m</i> (mM/l)			<i>n</i> (min ⁻¹)		
	Sol A	2A/3	A/2	Sol A	2A/3	A/2	Sol A	2A/3	A/2
KCl	65.00	65.00	90.00	58.80	58.82	41.66	0.063	0.066	0.079
K ₂ SO ₄	0.80	0.75	0.60	1.00	1.00	0.90	0.095	0.120	0.095
K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆	0.50	0.45	0.40	0.53	0.40	0.36	0.163	0.112	0.014

TABLE II

Effect of dialysis

Sol dialysed for (days)	Sp.Cond. × 10 ⁴ (mhos) at 25°	KCl			K ₂ SO ₄			K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆		
		<i>a</i> (mM/l)	<i>m</i> (mM/l)	<i>n</i> (min ⁻¹)	<i>a</i> (mM/l)	<i>m</i> (mM/l)	<i>n</i> (min ⁻¹)	<i>a</i> (mM/l)	<i>m</i> (mM/l)	<i>n</i> (min ⁻¹)
2	62.65	800	1428.60	0.097	2.20	0.95	0.140	1.00	0.62	0.103
3	27.34	400	526.31	0.091	1.70	1.11	0.117	0.80	0.71	0.086
4	11.40	100	235.30	0.082	1.40	0.80	0.070	0.70	0.71	0.071
5	6.00	75	100.00	0.080	1.10	1.00	0.065	0.50	0.71	0.064
6	4.18	50	71.43	0.055	0.90	1.00	0.060	0.45	0.59	0.059
7	3.27	40	58.82	0.048	0.70	0.95	0.052	0.40	0.52	0.042
8	2.15	30	27.80	0.043	0.60	1.00	0.042	0.35	0.50	0.040
9	1.56	20	20.88	0.041	0.50	0.87	0.039	0.30	0.50	0.037

TABLE III

Effect of non-electrolytes

		KCl			K ₂ SO ₄			K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆		
		<i>a</i> (mM/l)	<i>m</i> (mM/l)	<i>n</i> (min ⁻¹)	<i>a</i> (mM/l)	<i>m</i> (mM/l)	<i>n</i> (min ⁻¹)	<i>a</i> (mM/l)	<i>m</i> (mM/l)	<i>n</i> (min ⁻¹)
Methanol	(0.5 ml)	60	37.03	0.044	1.20	1.03	0.041	0.55	0.60	0.036
"	(1.0 "	50	33.33	0.036	1.15	1.01	0.039	0.50	0.58	0.031
"	(1.5 "	40	23.81	0.022	1.10	1.03	0.033	0.45	0.56	0.025
Ethanol	(0.5 ml)	50	35.64	0.046	1.15	1.00	0.042	0.50	0.60	0.382
"	(1.0 "	40	33.33	0.030	1.10	0.92	0.040	0.50	0.57	0.034
"	(1.5 "	30	22.22	0.023	1.00	0.95	0.031	0.40	0.52	0.026
Isopropanol	(0.5 ml)	45	40.00	0.036	1.05	1.13	0.039	0.45	0.60	0.030
"	(1.0 "	30	32.26	0.026	1.00	1.05	0.035	0.40	0.62	0.027
"	(1.5 "	20	21.74	0.020	0.95	0.97	0.032	0.30	0.52	0.019
Acetone	(0.5 ml)	40	45.45	0.035	0.95	1.13	0.040	0.40	0.56	0.028
"	(1.0 "	30	27.00	0.028	0.90	1.00	0.032	0.35	0.52	0.025
"	(1.5 "	20	16.66	0.019	0.80	0.94	0.027	0.30	0.54	0.023
Formamide	(0.5 ml)	15	20.00	0.015	0.70	0.65	0.020	0.20	0.42	0.020
"	(1.0 "	5	15.65	0.012	0.60	0.55	0.012	0.10	0.37	0.014
Dioxane	(0.5 ml)	40	60.66	0.043	1.00	1.16	0.032	0.45	0.55	0.032
"	(1.0 "	30	50.00	0.036	0.90	0.92	0.024	0.35	0.56	0.028
"	(1.5 "	10	31.25	0.028	0.85	0.90	0.020	0.30	0.57	0.021
Sol without non-electrolyte										
Urea 5 M	(0.5 ml)	60	45.45	0.052	1.25	1.12	0.043	0.55	0.65	0.042
"	(1.0 "	65	50.00	0.054	1.25	1.12	0.043	0.55	0.65	0.042
"	(1.5 "	65	50.00	0.054	1.30	1.24	0.045	0.60	0.75	0.045
Glycerol 50%	(0.5 ml)	65	50.00	0.055	1.25	1.12	0.043	0.55	0.65	0.042
"	(1.0 "	70	55.55	0.057	1.35	1.26	0.045	0.55	0.65	0.042
"	(1.5 "	80	50.00	0.060	1.40	1.32	0.046	0.65	0.82	0.046

$(a+m)$, and n (Table III). The extent of sensitisation by methanol, ethanol, isopropanol, acetone, formamide and dioxane is greater in the presence of increasing volume of these non-electrolytes. The sensitising powers of these non-electrolytes are in the following order :

Formamide > Acetone > Dioxane > Isopropanol > Ethanol > Methanol

On adding urea and glycerol, which have a stabilising effect, the values of a , $(a+m)$ and n increase instead of decreasing. The stabilising power of these non-electrolytes is in the order : Glycerol > Urea.

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